

Pilot Course for Sustainable Development of E-Learning Tools

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Abstract

Online learning allows offers a variety of advantages amongst which can be mentioned: increased productivity, learner customization, content flexibility, targeted features etc. Nevertheless, most learning management systems are subscription-based and can prove to be quite expensive. For educational purposes in academic activities, freemiums and open source LMS solutions are readily available. The current research study follows the development of a pilot course using Talent LMS e-learning platform, which fulfills current requirements for new teaching methods that are more attractive and interactive. The importance of e-learning tools is exacerbated in the current socio-economic environment, which is currently dominated by the SARS-Cov2 epidemic. Authors propose a customizable learning environment using ready to use design tools, but also CSS code for a targeted user experience. The methodology for designing a Web Development for 3D Printing Start-ups pilot course was thoroughly presented, highlighting the main structural components. Implementation was undertaken during a seven-day intensive summer school held at POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest from Romania. Received feedback helped improve the contents, presentation and the structure of the course.

Keywords: E-learning, Teaching Methods, Adaptability, Gamification.

Introduction

As the world changes, continuous progress is made with the purpose of offering a better quality of life. Technology is increasingly available and advanced, with many advantages and disadvantages as well. Newer generations embrace a new way of thinking and develop different life-principles.

Recent studies conducted by Nagashibaevna Y.K. (2019) have shown that students have progressively lost interest in studying and that is mainly since some areas of education do not keep up with modern teaching technologies. Although many students use technology daily, they seem to agree that there is a lack of innovative and technology appropriate learning content.

In June 2020 the European Data Portal (2020) concluded that the current socio-economic environment caused by the SARS-Cov2 epidemic is forcing the shift of learning experiences from face to face into an online environment. This also made the Commission to review the Digital Education Action Plan in 2020, which was intended to

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support the development of online learning at different levels of education across Europe. The necessity of cohesive and reliable e-learning tools is felt more astringently than ever before.

According to Eurostat (2020) in 2019, four in five young people (80%) aged 16 to 24 in the European Union (EU) had basic or above basic digital skills. Among EU Member States, Romania had the lowest share of individuals aged 16 to 24 with basic or above basic overall digital skills (56%). This shows that almost half of young Romanians do not have the necessary digital skills to access educational services online. To support the global efforts of maintaining an adequate educational process the European Commission (2020) offers a wide range of online learning resources for learners, teachers and educators during the outbreak of COVID-19.

Rapanta C. et al. (2020) concludes in his research that universities, now more than ever, should invest in teacher professional development of their faculty, for them to be updated on effective pedagogical methods with or without the use of online technologies.

Considering the abovementioned, the authors propose the design of an intuitive pilot e-course for sustainable development of e-learning tools. The course addresses *Web Development for 3D Printing Start-ups* in an attempt to create an interactive learning experience for users and encouraging participative development of educational e-tools.

Study Background and Methods

The current study proposes the development of a pilot course module using the online Talent LMS e-learning platform. The pilot course was designed and implemented within an intensive summer school program financed through a partnership Erasmus+ project. *TechHUB 4.0 - Technology and Entrepreneurship Education for Bridging the Gap in Smart Product Development*, is an international project with POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest (UPB) from Romania as the project leader, and partnering up with three other universities: Czestochowa University of Technology (PCz) from Poland, Lancaster University (LU) from the United Kingdom of Great Britain and “Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu (ULBS) from Romania. TechHUB 4.0 aims at delivering, with methods based on modern teaching technologies, especially based on web-based platforms and digital technologies – e-learning and interactive platforms, the knowledge of professors, industry specialists, researchers, managers, and entrepreneurs to young students wishing to become entrepreneurs in the additive manufacturing (AM) area. To address this main target, the pilot course on *Web Development for 3D Printing Start-ups* was custom designed using CSS coding within Talent LMS.

Most learning management systems (LMS) are subscription-based and can prove to be quite expensive, reaching up to four figures a month. For educational purposes in academic activities, freemiums and open source LMS solutions are readily available. Aside budget considerations, another reason for opting for a free LMS is the size of the application area. For small businesses with small staff, for example, the features of a free e-learning platform are more than satisfactory.

According to Chang J. (2020) from Finances Online TalentLMS is the top free solution for e-learning (Figure 1). It is a very flexible cloud hosted LMS designed to help users simplify how they facilitate online seminars, courses, and other training programs. The cloud powered LMS solution does not need installation, upgrade or a back-up, thus being very user friendly even for a beginner admin.

Figure 1: Talent LMS main e-learning platform features

The key features that made TalentLMS the optimum choice for TechHUB 4.0 implementation and pilot course development were the comprehensive analytics service, the gamification of content and the availability of feature customisation through CSS coding.

In association with Talent LMS, WIX was selected as the designated website builder, mainly due to its' competitive advantages for beginners through advanced designing tools, as stated by Jenner N. (2018). Using WIX learners created a personal website by using the Artificial Design Intelligence (ADI) that the platform provides. A step-by-step learning process revealed how to create a website, add and edit content for a 3D printing start-up business.

Pilot Course Development

TalentLMS can be deployed with an open Application Programming Interface (API), but it is also an excellent solution when using Cloud hosting. It can support various languages, so that the developed pilot e-course could be not only delivered in a native language, but also administrated and designed that way by admins and, respectively instructors. TalentLMS as the main web platform for designing and delivering the pilot e-course mainly due to the open source characteristics and the available pricing plans. It is one of the very few platforms which can run cloud based, can offer a free pricing plan, has an open source on CSS coding and also has a variety of interactive content design and development tools. Five registered users and unlimited unregistered users were available and divided in several ways throughout the pilot e-course development process, as follows:

- 1 super admin and four instructors (registered users) – initial design and development stage;
- 1 super admin, 1 instructor and 3 learners (registered users) – first testing stage of the e-course;
- 1 super admin and 4 learners (registered users) – pilot testing during the focus group;
- 1 super admin, 4 instructors (registered users) and 100 learners (unregistered users) – pilot testing during the intensive summer school.

Figure 2: Module Structure for the module Web Development for 3D Printing Start-ups

The pilot e-course can be completed by an unlimited number of students, without having to open a specific TalentLMS user account. Nevertheless, the capabilities of the platform allow the development of very large data bases, the main customer types targeted ranging from freelancers and small businesses to large enterprises. The e-learning platform supports a series of common devices, like Windows, Linux, Android, iPhone/iPad, Mac, Web-based, Windows Mobile. This facilitated the adaptation of the pilot course to mobile devices.

three more modules, namely: Product Design and Development of Smart Products; Business Plan Development for The Future Engineer as an Entrepreneur; Smart Product Computer Aided Design and 3D Printing. Thus, while completing the e-course, students were asked to develop a business plan, design and manufacture 3D printing applications, and also develop their own website where they must “sell” their 3D printed products.

Web Development for 3D Printing Start-Ups was used as a pilot-course mainly to gather information and feedback for the optimization of the other three modules such as structural optimization, information layout specific requirements, uploading assignments (Figure 6) and pop-quiz tasks (Figure 7). Thus, for the best optimization, the ongoing feedback method was chosen. Depending on what type of module students completed, they encountered assignments, pop-quizzes (Figure 7) and ongoing feedback forms (Figure 8).

The final e-course assignment was designed using CSS and allowed learners to upload: a text reply (own web page link); a file (PPT presentation of the start-up); video (demo pitch presentation of the start-up); audio (motto of the 3D printing start-up). After assignment completion learners can receive feedback from their instructors, make the appropriate amendments and reply (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Assignment 1 in CSS code – instructor interface; a) learner options before submitting answer; b) learner options after submitting answer

The pop-quiz was designed using several types of questions, such as: multiple choice answers, gap filling, ordering answers, drag-and-drop, free text and randomized. Thus, the instructor could choose bespoke methods for each group of learners (Figure 7). Instructors can define the question type and edit the content of the question using CSS code. Also, both questions and answers could be arranged in a specific order or randomized for each individual learner. Each of the questions had equal weights. The duration of the quiz could not exceed 15 minutes and learners would pass if they achieved 80% of the score. A maximum of two attempts were allowed on the test with a five minutes delay between attempts. In order to start the test a password was required, which students received during live online sessions with the instructors.

Figure 7: Pop-quiz within course content – instructor interface

The feedback form was designed based on the same rules as the pop-quiz, and it included open answer questions (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Ongoing feedback form – instructor interface

The key role of the feedback form was to establish if the proposed approach was more suitable for learners than traditional delivery of learning content. Throughout the pilot e-course, learners found the course rather interesting, funny and easy to follow. Moreover, as learners gave feedback on certain aspects, optimizations and modifications within the content and information layout was made.

Talent LMS has an integrated gamification process, where learners can get points when completing modules, pop-quizzes and registering. Instructors can also modify the gamification options and view student's progress, either individually or either the whole class. Thus, with interactive courses and current or new topics of interest, students should improve their activity within daily courses.

Conclusion

With no doubt, the future of teaching will be linked to e-learning tools and adapted to student's evolving needs. The designed pilot e-course could be used simultaneously with current teaching methods, focusing on advantages like:

- Presentations can be made within the e-learning Talent LMS platform, without any other specialized software;
- The physical attendance under certain specific aspects may no longer be mandatory;
- Learners can propose throughout the e-course feedback on what aspects can be further developed and improved;
- Learners can become involved in the active development of their own e-courses by learning how to use CSS code to customize their favorite features.

It seems that the conventional teaching methods need upgrade and an adaptation to the current requirements must be made.

Influenced by the current socio-economic developments caused by the SARS-Cov2 epidemic, the teaching process has greatly shifted in the online environment. Practice has shown that not all educational systems were ready for such a mass exodus, but they all made a real effort to adapt in a very short amount of time. Thus, an online attractive, intuitive and interactive platform must be used and adapted according to the current requirements, which shall also encompass the already existing platforms, all in one place. Students should access one platform for online meetings, course studies, pop-quizzes and uploading homework.

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